

Between Nollywood and Cultural Values: A Search for Authentic Global Medium in Democratic Nigeria

Charles Effiong

University of Calabar, Calabar-Nigeria

&

Bernard Eze Orji

Federal University, Ndufu-Alike Ikwo- Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Abstract

In any democratic system, the media are known to bear the voice of the masses by being at the centre of sustaining the hope of the people, who desire the promotion of their accepted cultural values vis a vis other socio-political and economic developments. In this light, there is high dependence on the media to visibly play this role of cultural promotion. Thus the Nigerian film industry, referred to as the Nollywood, sprang up to champion the course of cultural promotion and by so doing, also support the sustenance of democratic culture in the country. In the era of globalization, when world economies and cultures are being challenged in terms of peculiar developments, Nollywood is counted among the top three film industries that are accessible globally. However, while other film industries of the world are churning out narratives that positively promote their cultural and political ideologies, the Nigerian film industry seems not to be passionate about giving out the celebrated cultural values of Nigeria and is thus seen to be celebrating what many contend as tripe and sinister-filled content that negates the authentic promotion of cultural and democratic values of the country. To this end this paper seeks to examine how Nollywood can be refocused given the challenge of globalization to promote authentically accepted values of the Nigerian people. Therefore, the conclusion and possible suggestion is that the film should develop their themes from nationalistic struggle and similar situations that will tell the story of Nigeria better than stereotypical themes against authentic cultural values.

Résumé

L'avènement du système démocratique au Nigeria au milieu de l'année 1999 a suscité de l'espoir parmi les masses nigérianes, de sorte que les Nigériens privés de biens nationaux ont commencé à avoir le désir que de meilleures choses leur arrivaient. Cela reposait sur la conviction que le gouvernement sera dorénavant, du peuple, par le peuple et pour le peuple. Etant donné que les médias qui portent la voix des masses sont au centre de l'espoir du peuple, qui désire la promotion de ses valeurs culturelles acceptées par rapport aux autres développements socio-politiques et économiques; une forte dépendance vis-à-vis des médias pour ce rôle est devenue visible. Ainsi, l'industrie cinématographique nigériane, connue sous le nom de Nollywood, est née pour défendre le cours de la promotion culturelle et, ce faisant, elle peut également soutenir le maintien de la culture démocratique dans le pays. À l'ère de la mondialisation, lorsque les économies et les cultures du monde sont confrontées à des développements particuliers, Nollywood figure parmi les trois premières industries

cinématographiques accessibles à l'échelle mondiale. Cependant, alors que d'autres industries cinématographiques du monde produisent des récits qui promeuvent positivement leurs idéologies culturelles et politiques, l'industrie cinématographique nigériane ne semble pas être passionnée par la diffusion des célèbres valeurs culturelles du Nigeria et elle est donc considérée comme célébrant ce que beaucoup affirment comme bêtises, ayant un contenu sinistre qui nie la promotion authentique des valeurs culturelles et démocratiques du pays. A cette fin, cet article cherche à examiner comment le Nollywood peut être recentré étant donné le défi de la mondialisation pour promouvoir les valeurs authentiquement acceptées du peuple nigérian. Une technique d'enquête et d'inférence sera utilisée dans ce travail. Par conséquent, la conclusion et la suggestion possible est que les films devraient développer leurs thèmes de la lutte nationaliste et des situations similaires qui raconteront l'histoire authentique du Nigéria.

Introduction

Discourse on Nollywood has been trending in the public sphere since Nigerian popular films captured national and international audiences in the advent of the 21st century. Critical issues about the films have variously centred on the thematic preoccupation of the films produced by this industry. This issue is yet to be exhausted as many of the products from Nollywood are still under criticism tailored on being low in content and form. Lately, some products from the industry have started taking new forms and content that play down on image bastardization of Nigerian cultures, a number of the products can still be seen with issues of cultural muddling and negativism. To this extent, there has been a clear call for all to contribute to making the film industry in Nigeria a veritable source for cultural promotion whereby all that is to be produced by the industry carry with them the quality, authenticity and the positivity of the Nigerian culture. The *Cultural Policy for Nigeria*, inter alia, holds that culture is the totality of the way of life of the people that promotes their values and makes them to be identified accordingly. The document stresses further.

Culture is not merely a return to the customs of the past. It embodies the attitude of the people to the future of their traditional values faced with demands of modern technology which is an essential factor of development and progress. When, therefore, we talk of self-reliance, self-sufficiency and a natural identity as the core of our national development objectives, we are referring to culture as the fountain spring of all policies whether educational, social, political or economical that the people hold as their own. (1)

The essence of this is not far-fetched in the sense that irrespective of modernity the culture should be as authentic and original and acceptable as possible. Notably, film is widely acknowledged as a cultural product which portrays the culture or cultures of the people in the light that is attractive to the audience especially in the face of globalization. By implication, films should be able to market one culture to other cultures, protect its own culture from implosion, and make other cultures to identify with it. In doing this, the various aspects of that culture in politics, socials, economics, religion etc that are valuable would have to be protected and promoted. This is not to say that culture is not dynamic, but the very essence of one identifying with another's culture rests on the fact that such culture is not hostile and does not in any way tantamount to creating a negative impression on people. Implicitly, all cultures are supposed to be receptive with minimal space for unwarranted

criticism. For instance, the story about corruption in Nigeria has spotlighted the country and people in an unpleasant manner such that even Nigerians themselves are afraid of one another with no trust in business endeavours.

In a democratic setting, typical of a free competitive society that stimulates creativity, film industries have been able to selectively manage and market the cultural values of their countries to the global audience. This is evident in the various film narratives of top two film industries, the American Hollywood and the Indian Bollywood. A cursory view of what is produced by these countries attests to the fact that what they produce and market is for the glorification of their culture. For instance, the epic narrative, *Pearl Harbour*, a Hollywood production, which is an account of the United States of America exploit in World War II after being attacked by the Japanese Army expressly shows that America can protect their interest anywhere in the world and make themselves attractive and useful globally.

Such examples from the Hollywood have already suggested and made useful impact as models to Nollywood films producers. Now epic themes of high quality and appreciations e.g *October 1* and *1960* are being churned out by the industry for a better promotion of Nigerian cultural values, democratic principles among other peculiar elements that are shown to the audience instead of always producing what Okome refers to as themes that revolve around fertility or childlessness, polygamy, inheritance issues, prostitution, philandering, and infidelity (in Ayo Akinwale 22). This gives the reason in which this paper attempts to examine how to further help Nollywood be more focused on the promotion of cultural values of Nigeria than exposing and celebrating the tripe which the society detests.

Cultural Values and Globalization

A mere understanding of cultural values could be underscored through the prism of culture as that which is generally accepted to be the way of life of the people. Indeed culture is that which shapes people's lives, makes them known, gets other people to identify with them and distinguishes them as a peculiar breed as well as stimulating in them a sense of belonging in the society. The *Cultural Policy for Nigeria* aggregates all these thus:

Culture is the totality of the way of life evolved by a people in their attempt to meet the challenge of living in their environment which gives orders and meaning to their social, economic, aesthetic and religious norms and modes of organization, thus distinguished a people from its neighbours... culture comprises material, institutional philosophical and creative aspects (3).

There is no gainsaying the fact that the people have a primary purpose to protect their culture to the best of their ability and proof it as a pattern for their identification. Any contrary act against this would suggest imminent negative effect on the society which culture is not given adequate protection that is deserved. This contention also adopts the point of view that culture is the essence of the lifespan of any society and therefore it must not be trivialized and personalized. Eagleton gives an affirmation of this by considering culture as:

a kind of ethical pedagogy, which will fit us for political citizenship by liberating the idea of collective self-buried within each of us, a self which finds supreme representation in the universal realm of the state (7).

In culture, therefore, we have those elements the society values, and in a typical African environment, cultural values account for morality. Morality is key to the way of life of the people, and in this case people's cultures are conditioned based on moral values that are placed at a higher level. That is why a typical African community will pay regard to the "sense of community life, the sacredness of life, respect to religion, good human relationship, respect for authority, respect for elders, respect for truth, respect for own language, and respect for time" (Oliver Onwubiko 13). This assertion is a justification of the fact that values account for morality and enhances individual's or group's judgmental effort about their rational or irrational action and relationship with the society. No one thing, person or group of persons that is bad or act offensively is accepted in the society and this is the reason that the society always identifies, appreciates and celebrates what is adjudged as being good.

The foregoing suggests that cultural values hold the key to entice and trap people in the global sphere to identify with a particular culture. Obviously, the people whose cultural values are promoted would readily be proud at any given time at home and among other cultures. Reacting to this, Tracie Utoh-Ezeajugh holds that the people would find folktale activity fascinating through the expression of acceptable norms, ways of doing things, attitudes, values and taboos in the community (18), because those are what they value. Therefore, it may be safe to add that acceptable values and approved ways of behaviour in a given community account for a good appreciation and popularity of such culture.

Popularity has become prevailing in the world today owing to the fact that various cultures of the world especially those considered to be developed have pervaded those ones considered as developing. This development is viewed based on the effect of globalization, an ideology, which is seen to be aggravating the hegemony of western world over growing economies and cultures like Nigeria. A number of questions have been raised in this direction with the term, globalization, being labeled a declaration of war on other countries and as one that is not able to achieve liberal democracy and a common market place in the world (Uche Nwaozuzu 87). However, it cannot be taken away that the ideology gives the world a template for development and especially growing cultures that are upbeat to face global competition. A clear example is the 2015 general elections in Nigeria, where a ruling party conceded defeat to an opposition party after the western world had branded the country's electoral system and democracy as frail and at the brink of collapse. Beyond the expectation of cynics, it took the courage and determination of Goodluck Jonathan, then Nigeria's President, to prove to the world that Nigeria is developed and is working towards integration in the globalization grid.

This ideology therefore conditions developing cultures to face the competition of promoting their cultural values as other cultures that are known to be hegemonizing others do. Various channels for doing this are available and include sustenance of democratic principles, communication and media etc. Today, it is clear that many countries of the world have exploited the means of communication to compete in the global sphere. Notable among such countries are those in Arab continent with substantial establishment of media conglomerate such as Al Jazeera, Bein Television, CCTV etc in broad band, cable and satellite networks. Through these media, there have been adequate promotion of Arabic styles to transnational audience and not only what the west would have preferred. This has

further proven the competitive space the ideology has created for cultural values of all countries of the world to be promoted, so that in promoting the cultural values of the society that are authentic, the medium can become popularly accepted in the global sphere.

Nollywood, Cultural Values and Nigerian Democracy

Like Hollywood and Bollywood, Nollywood has triumphed in the global space especially among Nigerian and African audiences in general. Its success is rooted in the fact that it emerged when popular entertainment was becoming the global appeal for the audience. More so, the success is linked to the technical ability that is peculiar to films, to turn long narratives that would probably have taken many days to read and understand into a few hours of watching the screen, enjoying the actions and dialogue as well as understanding the message of the story. It is expected that the film industry should do more in terms of giving adequate concerns to the promotion of Nigeria's cultural values and democratic principles in order to fully and positively integrate itself and country in the globalization grid. Nevertheless, some of the productions by Nollywood have cultural value questions to answer which have made some of the productions not saleable beyond national boundary and at the same time cause national and transnational audience to disregard these productions; whereas these films ought to have always reflected the representation of how to construct a social world and everyday life (Douglas Kellner 1).

As clearly pointed out, films are export commodities that carry cultural, political, social, religious and even technological effects of the countries producing them in order that these elements can be appreciated by world audience. This is to say that films are often not produced to be localized because they are cultural products and medium of communication and diplomacy. This is made clear in the Hollywood example which Barclays Ayakoroma says has always kept faith with the reflection of American way of life culturally, politically, technologically, economically, socially etc (7). The American Hollywood template can serve as the reason the Nollywood should consistently produce films of good cultural values that would make every Nigerian audience and the world to be proud. This is not to say that Nigerian product should be subjected to American manipulations, but it is to say that such cultural products as films can be made to be qualitative if lessons on how themes on cultural promotion are learned from where quality standard is upheld. Implicitly, it would suffice to link this to an attempt to tap from the impact of globalization, which Douglas Anele strongly enthuses as a continuation of culture contact which helps in promoting languages, international cultural exchange, multiculturalism through news, music and movies in the media (10-11).

Issues of voodooism, magic, prostitution, wicked mother-in-law and the likes have over a period of undergoing critical perspectives from scholars been dropped by producers for certain alien and outrageous portrayal of the culture in the light that does not depict the true values of the people. These days one can see films that show extraordinary lifestyle and abuse of cultural principles and values. In this direction, Akinwale notes that:

In the film, *Eteketete*, by Corporate Picture, the film talked mostly of reproductive issues in the most banal of all forms. It made it look as if the Yoruba love to discuss issues of reproduction so freely among their families without restraint. This is not true. The same storyline can be seen in the films from the English producers of *Holy Harlot* by Chyke

Movie production and *The Secretary* by Konia Concept Ltd. Here, also, sex talk was engaged in openly. *Mr. Lecturer* by Chico Ejiro showed some of such sex orgies. Such films, I believe, does not augur well for Nigeria's cultural diplomacy (30-31).

Akinwale's position rightly points out that the content of current Nollywood films has betrayed the essence of Nigerian cultural values which form the product for international relationship. Based on the contention, Nigerian cultures may be prone to having even more difficulty in global acceptability politically and otherwise. Although these films, in form or genre, as melodramatic which prescribes warning and punishment on social vices, and could strike national and transnational appeal; the monotony with which the treatment of such vices are promoted calls for the worry that makes one to see such productions as negatives to cultural promotion. This is further reinforced when these films portray women in all negative forms to the global audience instead of celebrating and presenting them for international acceptability. A number of films such as *Blackberry Girls*, *Fishers of Men*, *Submission* etc have represented the female gender in the Nigerian society as ingrates, greedy, gluttons, sex workers among other loathsome identification tags. The content of *Blackberry Girls* and *Fishers of Men* are clearly the celebration of prostitution. Both films show how young Nigerian girls abuse the dignity of womanhood, go in search of men, steal from the men, and falsely display affluence, not contented with what they are given and what they have. *Submission* shows the pressure from a mother-in-law on the daughter to become unfaithful to her marriage as well as wanting to have a canal affair of her son-in-law. To this end, Chinyere Okunna submits that such portrayal is:

unrealistic, counter-productive and damaging to the cause of women because it can lead to subjugation of, increase men's disdain for women, sow distrust between men and women, undermine their confidence in themselves and strengthen the forces which push women to the background in this patriarchal society (34).

The above contention has proven a point that Nollywood has some questions to answer in terms of promoting Nigerian cultural values. Given the circumstance presented by globalization ideology, where competition and equality are the features, the presentation of female gender in this light suggests the debasement of the reverence the Nigerian cultures accord women, especially in present days when successive democratic governments have considered and offered women a near 35 percent slot in cabinet positions including some elective positions occupied by them. Without doubt, this appears to jeopardize the quality and relevance of women in playing competitive and equal roles in the Nigerian democracy. In the entire world, democracy is credited to be the best form of government to the extent that it can sustain development, promote cultural effects transnationally and enhance the participation of all citizens. In situations where suggestions are raised for peculiar democratic culture to suit Nigeria and Africa as a whole, such as *Afrocracy* recommended by Maitama Sule during the opening of maiden Faculty of Arts International Conference at the University of Calabar; sustaining evidence is that participatory elements which is characteristic of democracy should be part of any principle in governance. This is the reason it is emphasised that:

Democracy as a system of government thrives on constitutionality, citizens' participation, respect for the rule of law, delivery of services and the advancement and promotion of individual and collective freedom. These elements are the fundamental pillars

that differentiate democracy from other forms of governance. Indeed, the essence of democracy is that citizens must be able to ventilate their views through unrestrained debates and that there should be active citizens' participation in governance as well as unrestrained communication between the government and the governed (Umar Pate 3).

The media, in which film is part of, are popular vehicles for the promotion of cultural and democratic values, and it is what the media projects that one can say they have positively or negatively promoted these values. As earlier stressed, certain films by Nollywood which spotlights the female gender in bad perspective can conjure and provoke apathy from the women in the area of participation in national development. Lack of support for them, in this direction, and conditioned by the impact from the video film productions can further deter and restrain the women in contributing to democratic course and sustainable development.

However, with Teco Benson's film. The *Senator*, Ayakoroma vividly shows that Nollywood has been able to treat political issues and proffer ways of sustaining Nigerian democratic values following political hostilities captured in the film. According to him, the film unfolds the kind of politics played by Nigerian politicians and proffers "a warning to the political class that there are better and more decent approaches to playing politics" (20). This background gives the impression that Nollywood can promote quality values of democracy and thereby promotes authentic values of the Nigerian society and in some conditions those of other African countries in the global space.

This is not far-fetched based on the account of Moradewun Adejunmobi, who reveals that the films are popular in the Democratic Republic of Congo because audiences there see political and cultural situations in the films that are similar to their society; thus this popularity made their government to place a ban on patronage for Nollywood because members of local theatre groups felt that Nollywood was drawing away their audience (106). The popularity of the films in African continent is enhanced by the Multichoice DSTV Africa Magic Channels which carry almost all Nollywood films daily and hourly.

Conclusion

Searching for authentic global medium demands committed dependence on the promotion of the positives of cultural values in the Nigerian society. The fact is that as the world has become more competitive than ever owing to the globalization tendency, cultural products that are authentic, acceptable and responsive to the people can only be the one that draw positive interest and acceptance in the global sphere. Clear evidence has been stated about the American film industry, Hollywood, which thrives on promoting American cultural values in all spheres. This paper has attempted to demonstrate that Nollywood has done well in some parts and has failed in some parts. Notably, some thematic preoccupations of the films have truly fallen short of presenting the country's cultural values in good light for global appreciation, while some have done well to the extent of drawing transnational appeal especially in African continent. Therefore, to remain an authentic global medium, producers of Nigerian films need to search for themes such as nationalistic narratives that can be saleable even beyond Africa. This kind of stories gives genuine epic and historical fact about the way and lifestyle of the people to the present. Latest Nigerian video films such as *October 1* and *1960* are clear indications that the industry is set to

promote values that Nigerians would be proud of globally. It is expected that since there must always be a model or template for others to follow in development process; peculiar Nigerian stories with nationalistic impact that are prototypical of what many international audience celebrate in films are encouraged for promotion by film producers because such can further enhance the integration of Nollywood as a global medium.

Works Cited

- Adjunmobi, Moradewun. "Charting Nollywood's Appeal Locally and Globally". *Film in African Literature Today*. 28. Ernest Emenyonu (Ed). Ibadan: HEBN Publishers, 2010. 106 – 121. Print.
- Akinwale, Ayo. *Nollywood as an Instrument for Nigeria's Cultural Diplomacy: Reflections of A Cultural Administrator*. 4th Annual Public Lecture for National Institute for Cultural Orientation, Friday 16th August, 2013. Abuja: National Institute for Cultural Orientation, 2013. Print.
- Anele, Douglas. *Globalization, Cultural Identity and Nigerian Youths*. Abuja: National for Cultural Orientation. No Publication Date. Print.
- Ayakoroma, Barclays, "Re-inventing The Political Process in Nigeria Films: A Critical Reading of Tecu Benson's *The Senator*". *Nigerian Theatre Journal*. 12.2. (2014), 1-21. Print.
- Eagleton, T. *The Idea of Culture*. Oxford: Blackwell, 2000. Print.
- Federal Government of Nigeria. *Cultural Policy for Nigeria*. Iagos: Federal Government Printers, 1988. Print.
- Kellner, Douglas. "Film, Politics and Ideology: Reflections on Hollywood Films in the Age of Reagan" www.gseis.inca.edu/faculty/keller/essays/filmpoliticsideology. Retrieved 8th December, 2012. Web.
- Okunna, Chinyere. "Portrayal of Women in Nigerian Home Video Films: Empowerment or Subjugation". *Africa Media Review*. 10.3.3(1996). 21-36. Print.
- Nwaozuzu, Uche-Chinemere. "Theatre and Globalization: Emerging Trends in the Dialectics of Performance in Sub-Saharan Africa". *African Performance Review*. 3.1.(2009). 86-99. Print.
- Onwubiko, Oliver. *African Thought and Culture*. Enugu: Snap Press, 1991. Print.
- Pate, Umar. "The Broadcast Media and Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges". Paper presented at the Forum on the "Broadcast Media and Electioneering Campaigns in Nigeria" Organized by the Nigerian Television Authority Holding at Kaduna, Ibadan and Enugu, March 12 -22, 2007. Print.